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Title: Implementing Problem-Based Pedagogy for Undergraduate Students: Fostering Creativity and Enhancing English Proficiency.

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Abstract: Problem-based learning (PBL) is an instructional method that allows participants to practice needed skills, such as working in groups, collaborating, sharing information, and solving problems. This research article explores the use of problem-based teaching methods to foster creative thinking and enhance problem-solving skills among engineering students.

The article describes how Problem-based learning (PBL) was used as a pedagogical tool to help undergraduate students (a) cultivate creativity, (b) enhance English language proficiency, and (c) build teamwork and collaboration skills. Qualitative data is presented about the influence of the PBL experience on 72 undergraduate Software Engineering students of New Uzbekistan University during a semester-long PBL experience.

The initial findings indicate that engagement in PBL can help students begin to acquire the knowledge, skills, and attitudes needed for 21st century such as language proficiency, problem-solving, critical thinking, creativity and teamwork.

References:

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Biography:

Gulbakhor Mamadiyeva specializes in English Language Teaching (ELT), focusing on problem-based pedagogy, curriculum innovation, and student-centered learning. Her research interest areas are problem-based pedagogy, improving writing skills and the integration of active learning strategies to enhance language proficiency and creative thinking. She has presented at international conferences on educational technology, teacher training, and language assessment strategies.